

VillageMath Educational Review

An International/Multidisciplinary Journal of
Network for Grassroots Science and Mathematics
Education (The VillageMath Network)

A publication of VillageMath Educational Services
(CAC RC: 4097888)

Volume 7, Issue 1

July, 2025

CODEN: VERIAU

Effect of Blended Learning Instructional Strategy on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Genetics in Makurdi Metropolis

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16572784>

Article History: Received 21st June, 2025; Revised 21st July, 2025; Published 29th July, 2025.

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How to Cite this Article:

Michael-Aondoaseer, O. B., Adejoh, M. J., Okwara, O. K., Atsuwe, B.A. & Dagba, J. D. (2025). Effect of Blended Learning Instructional Strategy on Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Genetics in Makurdi Metropolis. *VillageMath Educational Review (VER)*, 7(1), 84-97.
<https://ngsme.villagemath.net/journals/ver/v7i1/michael-aondoaseer-adejoh-okwara-atsuwe-dagba>

Abstract

This study was carried out to investigate the effect of blended learning instructional strategy (BLIS) on secondary school III students' achievement in Genetics in Makurdi metropolis, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated. The study adopted quasi experimental research design of non-randomized pretest post-test control group type.

The population of the study was 2100 while a sample of 186 SS3 Biology students (made up of 125 males and 65 females) was drawn from four secondary schools using multistage sampling technique. The research instrument was the Genetics Achievement Test (GAT). The instrument was trial tested on 30 students. The Kuder-Richardson formula 21 was used to determine the reliability coefficient of GAT which was 0.84. The research questions were answered using mean while hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using ANCOVA. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Genetics using BLIS and students taught with the traditional method. There was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught genetics using BLIS. The study recommends that since BLIS has been found to enhance students' achievement in Genetics, Biology teachers should be encouraged to adopt the instructional strategy for teaching topics in Biology. It was also recommended that the Ministries of Education should incorporate the method in Biology curriculum.

Keywords: Blended Learning, Academic Achievement, Biology Education, Genetics, Secondary Education, Teaching Methods

Introduction

Genetics is a concept in the Biology curriculum for all Nigerian senior secondary schools (SSS). It is the study of heredity and variation. Heredity is a biological process where a parent passes certain genes onto their children or offspring. These genes carry some specific traits which are expressed in the offspring. Some of these traits may include physical characteristics and natural talents (Abimbola & Bello, 2024; Etobro & Banjoko, 2017). Variation explains the differences that occur as genes are passed from one generation of organisms to the other.

Akilu and Umar (2023) sees Genetics as the cornerstone of modern biology, which conveys vital information on inheritance, evolution, and the very bases of life. Genetics is a vital aspect of everyday life that helps determine a child's true paternity, blood group, and genotype. The study of Genetics covers issues ranging from genetic technologies to the social, legal, and ethical issues involved and many others. It also leads to several discoveries and also brought about an increase in the nations crop improvement in genetically modified food and organisms (Abbas & Idris 2024; Mohammed & Ganiyu, 2022).

Topics covered under Genetics in the SSS level include genes and chromosomes, genetic concepts, variations, mitosis and meiosis, monohybrid crossings, and many others (Federal Republic of Nigeria - FRN, 2018). Most of these topics are abstract in nature as they require some mental effort for proper comprehension. Because of this, most students tend to see genetic concepts as difficult, leading to poor achievement of students which is corroborated by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) (2009, 2010, 2012, 2013, 2015) Chief Examiners' Report (CER) which specifically reported that most Biology students did not attempt questions related to genetics and that those who attempted it also performed poorly. In the years 2010, 2012, 2016 and 2017, students were reported to have demonstrated poor knowledge of genetic crossing and did not understand that the XX and XY chromosome pair govern human sex determination; instead, they were using other alphabets like M for male and F for the female when answering questions related to genetics

(Mohammed & Ganiyu, 2022). This affects the achievement of Biology students in external exams (WAEC Chief Examiners Reports). This poor achievement will later affect national manpower, as many students cannot study courses such as Genetic Engineering, Genetic Mapping, Medicine and many others in higher learning institutions.

Academic Achievement in genetics and Biology as a whole is the individual students' learning gain after being exposed to a certain form of assessment in the subject (Zhen & Mustapha, 2022). Akilu and Umar (2023) also noted that students' academic achievement is the actualization of specific educational objectives set by an educational institution or curriculum. Students' academic achievement is usually based on tests, examinations, and response to situations outside the classroom, among others. This determines the extent to which a student has acquired knowledge of the concept taught (Njoku, 2024). For this study, students' academic achievement shall be in the context to which Genetics students can remember and express what has been learnt from the classroom without any form of help from any teacher. In this regard, student achievement in genetics could either be low or high, it will be low when the students do not obtain the desired expectation or mark of the instructor, and it is high when the mark obtained by the learners is exactly or above the desired outcome of the instructor (Micheal-Aondoaseer, Adejoh, Okwara & Uduaka, 2023). If students' academic achievement in genetics will be improved upon, there is need for the introduction of new and innovative teaching methods in the classroom, this will avail learners the opportunity to see, view, and possibly hear instructions that are perceived to be difficult in simpler form (Adeyemi & Adeoye 2023).

Innovative teaching is very possible these days because of the introduction of technology. Teachers can use different learning approaches aided by technology to concretize a concept like genetics that is abstract in nature. Researchers like Adelana and Ajayi (2020) and Assuah, Agyei and Ateko (2024) noted that engaging technology at bringing about improved achievement of students in genetics and biology as a whole would be a good idea if found to be effective. One of the innovative teaching strategies that could be achieved with technology is Blended Learning Instructional Strategy (BLIS). Scholars gave different definitions as to what Blended Learning is. Graham, Borup, Short, & Archambault (2019) sees BL as the combination of face-to-face instruction with online learning experiences. University Grant Commission [UCU] (2021) defines it as the art of adding digital learning tools with more traditional classroom face-to-face teaching. BL is a teaching strategy that combines varying teaching modalities to achieve a learning outcome (Njoku, 2024). Blended Learning when used as an instructional strategy in the classroom, comes with a lot of learning advantages to the student, teacher, and the school community. Blended Learning Instructional Strategy (BLIS) avail learners the opportunity to learn at their own pace, because it is highly flexible and can accommodate different resources from the internet which the teacher can instruct the learners to access after the class (Nurhikmah, Tahmir, Junda, & Bena, 2018; Al Mashikhi & Soliman, 2018). BLIS offers a foundation for greater interaction between students, learning content, and teachers. BLIS has the capability of motivating students to higher achievement by bringing about higher gains in achievement when compared to conventional teaching methods (Cleveland-Innes & Wilton, 2018). Roinah, Ika, Triana, Titin and Mahsuri (2024) noted that BLIS helps students to work together, support one another and as well as discover one another weakness. They also noted

that BLIS also helps the teacher to generate data from online activities which can be used to personalize instruction to each student in the onsite classroom. It is expedient that instructional strategies in Biology are looked in to if students' achievement will be improved upon. Sometimes when students' achievement is high, there is a general assumption that such a learner with high achievement would be a boy, this shows that student achievement has been related to gender. Some researchers believe gender plays a dominant role in student achievement while others do not.

Gender is seen a factor that may affect students' achievement in learning genetic concepts (Areji & Onuba 2022). Gender is the attribute of being called a male or female with a corresponding feature (Nnamani & Oyibe, 2016). There are different opinions when it comes to the particular gender that achieve excellently. Most often, people believe that male students achieve better in genetics than their female counterparts, and researchers have always sought to validate this assertion. However, there is no scientific proof for that. Akilu and Umar (2023) and Katcha and Wushishi (2015) discovered that gender does not influence the achievement of students, while Okwara, Anyagh and Ikyaan (2017) and Odagboyi (2015) noted that male students achieve significantly better than female students. Studies conducted on gender show that there is inconsistency in achievement of male and female students. Therefore, this study also seeks to investigate the effect of gender on the achievements of students in Genetics, especially when it comes to the use of BLIS.

Nnoli and Ugwuoti (2024) conducted a study with 87 Biology students in Awka educational zone Nigeria, investigating the effect BL approach on secondary school students. The findings of the study revealed that students taught with BL significantly improved in their interest in learning biology more than those in the control group. Similarly, Batican and Geronimo (2025) examined blended learning approach and its implications for students, academic performance in physical science using a sample size of 178 students from Albuera Leyte. The findings show that the blended learning group demonstrated significantly higher post-test scores and achievement gains compared to the modular learning group. Nurhikmah *et al.* (2018) took a study to consider the issue of Blended Learning Media in the Biology Classroom in Indonesia. Developmental survey design research was used using the Hannafin and Peck model. The respondents were grade 11 students of Biology in Negeri 1 Barru, Indonesia. Questionnaires, interviews, observations, and documentation were used to descriptively analyze the data from the study. The result of the need assessment showed that it is essential to develop blended-based learning media for Biology to improve students' self-learning skills and explore their other individual skills.

Relatedly, Maureen *et al.* (2022) researched on BLIS as a tool for improving students' academic achievement in Biology in Delta State of Nigeria. Findings showed a significant difference in the post-test achievement scores of students exposed to the BLIS and those taught without it, in favour of students exposed to the lesson using BLIS. Similarly, Njoku (2024) investigated the effect of BL method on students' academic achievement in Biology. The study was carried out in secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, Nigeria, with a sample size of 100 students. The result revealed that there is a significant difference in the mean score of students taught Biology with BL and those taught with discussion method in favour of BL. In another study, Asseke and Fabinu (2022) looked into the efficacy of a

blended learning approach (BLA) on students' academic achievement and retention ability in genetics in Alimosho-Lagos State, Nigeria. The result from ANCOVA showed a statistically significant difference in the academic achievement of students taught Genetics using the BLA and those taught using the lecture method. There was no statistically significant difference in the retention ability scores of both groups.

These related empirical works have links to students' achievement in Genetics. However, the related works are different because of the level of education, geographical limitation, methods of teaching, population, sample size and instrument used for data collection. To bridge the yawning gaps, the study seeks to Ascertain the difference in the achievement between male and female students. It is against this background that this study seeks to distinguish the effect of BLIS on achievement of students in Genetics in Makurdi metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Genetics using BLIS and those taught without BLIS?
- ii. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Genetics using BLIS?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Genetics using BLIS and those taught without BLIS.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Genetics using BLIS.

Methodology

This study adopted the quasi-experimental design, using the non- randomized pretest posttest non-equivalent control group design. The population of the study consists of 2100 senior secondary school III (SS3) students of Biology in Makurdi metropolis of Benue State, Nigeria. The SS3 students were chosen because genetics is scheduled to be taught at that level (FRN, 2018); they are familiar with Biology and have also been exposed to the traditional way of teaching Biology right from SS1. The sample for this study is 186 students (125 males and 61 females) drawn from the SS3 Biology student. Four schools in the metropolis were selected using multistage sampling techniques. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the schools that were involved in the study. In each of the four schools selected, simple random sampling was used to select one intact class. Two of the schools were designated as experimental while the other two were the control. The experimental groups were taught with the BLIS while the control groups were taught using the traditional teaching method or lecture method.

The instrument for the study was the Genetics Achievement Test (GAT) which was adapted from WAEC past questions on topics that are related to the content covered in the lesson plans. The GAT consists of two sections; section A contains the background

information of the respondents (class, time allowed and gender) while section B contains the questions. Trial testing was carried out to determine the internal consistency of the instruments. The result collected from trial testing GAT was analyzed using Kuder-Richardson formula 21 which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84. This formula was used because the items are scored dichotomously. GAT consists of 40 items which are multiple-choice objective questions with four options (A, B, C, & D) in which the students are expected to pick the one they consider as the correct option. The total mark obtainable from GAT is 40 marks.

Eighty-five (85) students in the experimental group received instruction for six weeks using the BLIS, which combines in-person instruction with online learning via devices. Under the research assistants' guidance, the students completed a variety of tasks and investigations during the class. The lesson's "student-centered" design is one of its crucial features. In the same vein, for six weeks, the 101 students in the control group received instruction in accordance with the traditional approach after which a post-test (GAT) was administered to the students across both groups. Mean was used to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The choice of ANCOVA is due to the fact that it statistically removes the initial differences across the non-randomized groups. This level of significance formed the basis for rejecting or not rejecting each of the hypotheses.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Genetics using BLIS and those taught without BLIS?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Score and Standard Deviation of Students Taught Genetics with BLIS and those Taught using the Traditional Method

Group	N	Pre-GAT		Post-GAT		Mean Gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
BLIS	85	8.93	5.47	29.88	7.09	20.95
Traditional method	101	8.68	6.31	25.80	7.19	17.12
Mean Diff		0.25		4.08		3.83
Total	186					

In Table 1, the result shows the mean achievement scores of students taught Genetics with BLIS and those taught without BLIS in Makurdi Metropolis. The result showed that in the pre-test, the students taught Genetics with the BLIS, and traditional

method had a mean score of 8.93 and 8.68 with corresponding standard deviations of 5.47 and 6.31 respectively. The mean score difference in the pre-test examination is 0.25 which shows that the two groups are at close cognitive level before the post-test examination. The result also showed that in the post-test examination, the students taught Genetics with BLIS and Lecture method had a mean score of 29.88 and 25.80 with corresponding standard deviations of 7.09 and 7.19 respectively. The mean score difference between the two groups is 3.83, which was in favour of the students taught Genetics with BLIS.

Research Question Two

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Genetics using BLIS?

Table 2: The Mean Achievement Score and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Taught Biology with BLIS

Group	N	Pre-BAT		Post-BAT		Mean Gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Male	35	7.49	4.96	32.14	5.58961	24.65
Female	50	7.66	4.46	28.30	7.09361	20.64
Mean Diff		0.17		3.84		4.01
Total	85					

In Table 2, the result shows the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Genetics with BLIS. The result showed that in the pre-test, the male and female students taught Genetics with BLIS had a mean score of 7.49, and 7.66 and corresponding standard deviations of 4.96 and 4.46 respectively. The result also showed that in the post-test examination, the male and female students had a mean score of 32.14, and 28.30 and corresponding standard deviations of 5.59 and 7.09 respectively. The mean score difference between the two groups is 4.01, which was in favour of the male students. This implies that the male students who learnt Genetics with BLIS had higher achievement scores as compared to the female students.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Genetics using BLIS and those taught without BLIS.

Table 3: Result of ANCOVA on Achievement Scores for Students Taught Biology Using BLIS and Those Taught Lecture Method.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	855.515 ^a	2	427.757	8.527	.000	.085	
Intercept	48004.983	1	48004.983	956.981	.000	.839	
PRETEST	87.045	1	87.045	1.735	.189	.009	
METHODS	778.908	1	778.908	15.528	.000	.078	
Error	9179.818	183	50.163				
Total	152408.000	186					
Corrected Total	10035.333	185					

Table 3 is the result of the ANCOVA which shows that $F(1, 183) = 15.528$. The p -value = 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using BLIS and those with Traditional method was rejected. The result implies that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology with BLIS and those taught with traditional method in Makurdi Metropolis.

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Genetics using BLIS.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result of Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students taught Biology with BLIS

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	403.678 ^a	2	201.839	4.329	.016	.096	
Intercept	18460.884	1	18460.884	395.955	.000	.828	
PRETESTEXP	99.641	1	99.641	2.137	.148	.025	
GENDERBLIS	310.436	1	310.436	6.658	.012	.075	
Error	3823.145	82	46.624				
Total	80128.000	85					
Corrected Total	4226.824	84					

The result of ANCOVA presented in Table 4 shows that the $F(1, 82) = 6.658$. The p -value = 0.012 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This shows that the null hypothesis is rejected. The result implies that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Biology with BLIS in Makurdi Metropolis.

Discussion

The result of the study in Tables 1 and 3 showed that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement of SS3 students taught genetics with BLIS and those taught without. This implies that the experimental group improved on their achievement in Biology than the control group. The findings of the study agree with Sumathi and Ebenezer (2021) that students taught with BLIS improve more in their achievement than their counterparts taught with Lecture method. Similarly, Nair and Bindu (2016), and Dwiastuti, Widoretno, Ramli, Saputra and Prabowo (2021) attest that BLIS had better impact on students' academic achievement in their own study, where the students taught with BLIS perform better than the students in the control group.

This can be justified for the reason that BL is a stimulating instructional strategy that propels students' attention and improves their achievement through its capacity to integrate different segments that allows students opportunity for proper lesson visualization. BL allows for active cognitive processing of abstract information, integrating real-world applications and case studies into lessons and demonstrating the practical relevance of Biology to the students which deepens their understanding and motivation to learn. Since BL offers varying resources beyond the normal textbooks in the conventional classroom which provides information in different formats to learners. BLIS, when used, caters for the different learning styles of students, making the Biology lessons more comprehensible to students. These factors and many others support the justification that BLIS enhances academic achievement of Biology students compared to the lecture method.

The findings of the study shown on table 2 and 4 reveals that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught genetics using BLIS in favour of the male students. The finding of this study disagrees with the findings of Nwaokolo (2023) and Michael-Aondoaseer *et al* (2023) who observed no significant difference in the achievement of male and female students taught Biology. The findings of Okwara, Anyagh and Ikyaan (2017) however agrees with the findings of this study that there is a significant difference in the achievement of male and female students in favour of the male students.

The findings are owing to varying degrees of factors like learning environment, because BL operates a traditional classroom and also infused a rotational digital/online environment which has some procedures to follow especially navigating the internet to gain access to quizzes, resources and videos for the class. All this may be too cumbersome for the female students in the study's sample, hence the reduction in their achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that BLIS is more effective for improving students' achievement in Makurdi Metropolis compared with the traditional method of teaching. The study also revealed that a significant difference exists in the male and female students' achievement taught Genetics with BLIS which is in favour of male students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Ministries of Education, State Secondary School Education Boards and other Educational stakeholders are encouraged to promote the use of BLIS in schools by organizing conferences, seminars and workshops for serving Biology teachers to learn or update themselves on the use of BLIS.
- ii. Guidance counsellors should organize counseling sessions for female students so as to bridge the achievement gap between them and their female counterparts via the use of BLIS in genetics.
- iii. Curriculum planners should make modifications in the curriculum as a matter of necessity to reflect the use of BLIS for improvement in the achievement of students in genetics.
- iv. School Administrators and inspectors should train and ensure Biology teachers incorporate the use of BLIS in Biology teaching.
- v. Biology teachers should be taught and encouraged to use BLIS in their classrooms so as to promote and encourage social interactions, self-motivation and active engagement among learners of both genders.

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